

PALESTINE AND PALESTINIANS IN INDIAN IMAGINATION AND RESEARCH STUDIES

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Abstract:

India has always remained very close to the Arab issues and historically, it firmly stood with the issue of Palestine. India's support for the Palestinian cause is an integral part of the nation's foreign policy. In 1988, India became one of the first countries to recognize the State of Palestine. In 1996, India opened its Representative Office to Palestine in Gaza City, which was later shifted to Ramallah in 2003. India has always played an active role in extending support for the Palestinian cause across various multilateral forums. The issue of Palestine and the Palestinians has always remained a very important part of academic activities around the world. The sufferings of Palestinians and the atrocities carried out by Israel has always been a matter of concern for civil society and academia in India. Being a researcher working on India-West Asia, I have a close watch on the issues related to Palestine.

It is now time to explore as how Palestine and the Palestinians are perceived among the Indian academics and researchers, and how the scholarly discourses have been changing with the shift in geo-strategic and economic situations in Palestine, particularly from the Cold War period to the globalization from the latter part of twentieth century to the beginning of the twenty first century where we see the new dimensions and challenges before the researchers in understanding the issues related to India Arab relations.

A 'Content Analysis' research technique using both the qualitative and quantitative methods will be used while interpreting and coding the textual material available in books, research papers and doctoral

theses. The objectives of this study is to examine and discuss the Indian academics and researcher's approaches towards the Palestinian issue in recent decades and also to point out the neglected themes and issues that are of much relevance in the present times.

Keyword: Palestine, India, Israel-Palestine Conflict, Refugee, Hamas, PLO, Literature, Doctoral Thesis

India has always enjoyed a cordial relationship with the Arab world since early ages. Even before Islam arrived in the Indian subcontinent, both regions were in constant contact. Arabs' connection to India predates the spread of Islam because they were familiar with the country through regular commercial trips. Arab seafaring was common along India's western and southern coasts, culminating in Arab settlements in various parts of the country. Historical evidence suggests that ideas and knowledge were regularly exchanged between the two regions. For example, during the Abbasid Caliphate, many important Indian books were translated into Arabic, and a number of Indian scholars were employed in the Abbasid Caliphate's courts for translation work. Both the regions being interdependent on each other resulted in exploring more knowledge since last four and five decades, a large number of expatriates working in various parts of Arab world have compelled Indian scholars to explore more about them.

Since last quarter of the 20th century, there can be seen the flow of academic writings and researches on India-Arab relations covering the diverse themes and issues related to area of international relations in a social science framework. In this academic development, the role of some government funded Centre for West Asian Studies and also universities are worth noting, which are presently engaged in exploring India's current economic and geo-strategic inclination towards the Arab Islamic world. The issue of Palestine is one of the major themes that academia is taking up with in the Arab world. Keeping in view the above issues of concerns, it looks inevitable that a stock of analysis of our previous researches be examined rather critically, in order to pave the way for the researchers of new generation.

This research paper aims to explore the themes and contents of the researches on Teaching and Research in Palestinian Studies in India carried out by the scholars in Indian universities since last four or five decades. The objective of this study is also to assess the importance of

these emerging themes and issues related to Palestinian issue. In this paper we will examine and discuss the Indian academics and researchers approaches towards the issues related to Palestine and Israel-Palestine conflict in recent decades, and also try to point out the neglected themes and issues that are of much relevance in the present times.

Arab Studies in India

What are distinct features of the research centers funded by the government of India? It can also be seen that in the area of international studies, the Arab Islamic world is becoming the most important areas of researches among the academics and policy makers in India. How these teaching and research centers are dealing with the issues to Palestine and the sufferings of Palestinians? How many centers of Arab studies are working in India? Although, these can be counted on fingers but the idea of West Asian Studies (or Middle Eastern Studies) started a few years after the independence of India in 1947. Although, the teaching and research in Islamic studies has already started soon after the arrival of Islam in Indian Sub-Continent.

For example, the Center of West Asian Studies (DAWANA 2024) at the Aligarh Muslim University, (AMU) was established in 1967 as a multi-disciplinary centre primarily focusing on contemporary problems and issues pertaining to West Asia and Africa. This Center offer Ph. D as well Postgraduate, Undergraduate and Diploma courses in West Asian Studies covering mainly the society, religions, economy and politics.

The Centre for West Asian Studies (CWAS 2024) at Jawaharlal Nehru University, (JNU) was established in early 1970s in New Delhi and it conducts teaching and research programmes covering countries of Arab world. This Centre offers Ph.D., Postgraduate, Undergraduate, and Diploma courses in West Asian Studies, focusing on society, religions, economy, and politics.

The Centre for West Asian Studies at Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU) was founded in the early 1970s in New Delhi, and it conducts academic and research programmes on Arab countries. The Centre offers M. Phil and Ph. D programmes. The third, the Centre for West Asian Studies, was established in July 2004 in New Delhi by Jamia Millia Islamia (JMI), a central university, as part of a research and development programme to provide students with modern education. It also aims to

provide a forum for informed exchange of ideas among students, faculty, and scholars from outside, who can understand West Asian region which has close and historic cultural, economic and religious links with India. It also seeks to promote an Indian perspective on developments in the region, especially those which equally impinge on global peace, security and development. In this regard, Centre for West Asian Studies, School of International Relation and Politics, Mahatma Gandhi University, Kerala is also important.

However, it is not that only West Asian Centers in the country are specifically doing researches on the issues related to the Arab world. In fact, various universities teach about this region in their main stream departments and even researches and Ph. D theses are written in these departments.

Palestine and India

India's strong support to Palestine is a well known fact and India remained a vocal supporter of Palestine since its independence till early decades of 21st century. However, the growing relationship between India and Israel in many fields including defense and agriculture during the last few decades has attracted research scholars in a big way and scholars are engaged in writing on Israel besides Palestine. A number of doctoral theses have been successfully submitted in several research centers focusing on several aspects of India's relation with Palestine.

In recent decades, the growing relationship between India and Israel in fields such as defence and agriculture has attracted the interest of research scholars, who are now writing about Israel in addition to Palestine. Several doctoral theses on various aspects of India's relationship with Palestine have been successfully submitted in a number of research institutions.

Researchers at Indian universities are also interested in Indo-Palestine relations. The researcher presents a historical perspective on Indian support for Palestine. India has consistently supported the Palestinian cause since their freedom struggle. During the pre independence period, the Indian attitude was represented by the Indian National Congress and its prominent leaders such as Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru. In recent years, there is a growing perception that India should play a more direct and mediatory role in the Israel-Palestine Peace process. While

India has shown some interest in this regard and this is welcomed by the Israelis and the Palestinians, the domestic discourse on India's new role is sharply divided. (Tripathy, 2012, pp. 236–245)

Academic Contributions

The following section briefly focuses on some of the issues related to contemporary researches on Palestine. In their five decades of existence, the government funded West Asian Studies Centers in India are engaged in the teaching and research activities related to Arab world, and the non-Arab countries like Iran, Turkey, and Israel are also included in this list. More than four hundred Ph. D theses completed during the last five decades in the Indian Centers run under the Central universities in which 35 theses are on Palestine. These doctoral researches comprise on different aspects of India-Palestine relations including the international dimension of Palestinian conflict. Most of the researches broadly cover the different aspects of Indo-Palestine relations.

For example the Ph. D thesis titled "*India and the Question of Palestine 1980-1993*" submitted to Jamia Milia Islamia, New Delhi explores India's foreign towards Israel and the strong support of India to the Palestinians. The British occupation of India and Palestine, as well as post-independence Indo-Palestine relations, have been extensively discussed. Before India's independence in August 1947, Indian leader Mahatma Gandhi's crystal clear vision and foreign policy paved the way for a very positive direction in support of the Palestinian cause, rejecting Israeli occupation of Palestine and Zionist and Jewish movements in general.

Before independence, as president of the Indian National Congress, Jawaharlal Nehru advocated for Palestinian rights on their own land, accusing Jews of serving British vested interests. When India gained independence and Nehru became the country's first prime minister, he maintained the same views on the Palestine issue. Nehru walked on the way of Gandhi and expressed sympathy for the suffering of Jews in Europe, but he believed that when it came to the Israeli occupation of Palestinian territory, Arabs were fighting British imperialism while Jews were promoting imperialist interests.

Nehru elaborates his views on same issue and writes: —Palestine, being a holy land for Christian, Jews and Muslims and its old history and associations attracts a great deal of attention. The roots of the problem in Palestine lie not in religion but in British imperialist policies. British

Policy which has created a special minority problem here-that of the Jews and the Jews side with the British and oppose the freedom of Palestine, as they fear that this would mean Arab rule. On the Arab side are numbers, on the other side great financial resources and the world-wide organization of Jewry. (Abu Jazer, 2018, p. 127)

Another researcher in a doctoral research titled *India's Palestine Policy since 1992* examines India's policy towards Palestine since 1992. The Indira Gandhi era saw a significant improvement in Indo-Arab relations. She expressed a strong interest in Arab world affairs, with a special concern for the Palestinian people. India supported the Arab position on the Palestine issue at UN and Non-Aligned Movement Summits. India became the first non-Arab country to recognize the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) as the "sole legitimate representative of the Palestinian people," allowing it to open an office in New Delhi. PLO leader Yasser Arafat was invited to visit New Delhi and diplomatic relations were established.

When India's Janata Party took power in 1977, there were rumours of a shift in its Palestine policy. Surprisingly, the Janata Government reaffirmed India's support for Arabs, including Palestinians, and expressed support for any peace initiative between Arabs and Israel. In 1980, Indira Gandhi was re-elected with a landslide majority and remained committed to supporting the Palestinian cause. On March 26, 1980, India's Foreign Minister, P.V Narasimha Rao, announced in Parliament that the PLO office in New Delhi would be granted full diplomatic recognition, granting it the status of an embassy with all diplomatic privileges.

Rajiv Gandhi (1984-1989) followed in the footsteps of his mother and grandfather. In November 1988, he recognized the State of Palestine, and the PLO office in New Delhi became the Embassy of the State of Palestine.

Between 1947 and 1991, India's West Asia policy was pro-Arab and anti-Israeli. India's stance was influenced by its interest in the Middle East, sympathy for Arabs, commitment to the UN, the Non-Aligned Movement (NAM), and minority sentiments. In addition to the Government support, the people of India have always come forward in support of the Palestine issue. This is evident from the numerous campaigns and demonstrations against Israel's actions in Palestine by

several civil society groups from time to time. Moreover, frequent seminars and conferences have also been organized in the country in the recent past to raise awareness and garner support for the just cause of Palestine. (Tripathy, 2012, pp. 236–245)

First Indian Prime Minister of India, Jawaharlal Nehru's attitude towards Palestine problem has been researched in a doctoral thesis in which the research scholar has concluded that "Nehru was convinced that the Palestine problem was created by the British and would never be solved by the British. Nehru rightly felt that this problem be solved by ignoring the British and coming to an agreement with each other. Being very vocal on this issue of Palestine he elaborated his points to make it clear that you cannot solve this problem by trying to crush the Arab people and it will not be settled by the British but by the two main parties coming to an agreement". (Sultan, 2006, pp. 210–211)

A doctoral thesis was submitted on "*India and the problem of Palestine*" in which the scholar has argued that "as long as the Palestinian Arab refugees will remain homeless, there can be no recognition of the fact that Israel has a right to exist at a place from where its rightful owner have been ousted to suffer till eternity. Mahatma Gandhi once said: I have all my sympathies with the Jews. But sympathy does not blind me to the requirements of justice. The cry for the national home for Jews does not make much appeal to me". (Shamsi, 1968, pp. 109–110)

Another doctoral research successfully tried to present the Indian perspective to the historical evolution of the Arab-Jewish Conflict-1881-1948. The scholars says that "for hundreds of years, Arabs and Jews have coexisted in Palestine in peace and harmony. The Muslim Arab conquest of Syria-Palestine in the 7th century AD improved conditions and religious tolerance for Jews. Except for a brief interruption during the Crusader period, Palestine in general and Jerusalem in particular have been an integral part of the Arab-Islamic civilization since the Arab conquest. Jews fleeing anti-Semitic Europe found refuge in the Arab and Muslim world. Prior to the emergence of political Zionism, Palestine provided the best example of peaceful coexistence of Arabs and Jews. Palestine was a predominantly Muslim country with a Christian minority and a small Jewish population. The majority of Jews in Palestine in the first half of the nineteenth century were descendants of Spanish refugees known as "sphardim," and the minority was immigrants from Russia and Eastern Europe known as "Ashkenazim." The Jews congregated in

Jerusalem, Hebron, Safad, and Tiberias". (Vincent, 2006, p. 309)

There are a number of book chapters in edited books appeared during the last four-five decade. Most of them deal with India's bilateral relation with Palestine. Prof. Mohammad Gulrez's chapter "*Mahatma Gandhi, Jawahar Lal Nehru and the Palestine Issue*" discusses Palestinian polices of Mahatma Gandhi and Jawaharlal Nehru. This study is heavily based on Gandhi's political views on the formation of Israel, as he believed that the current situation in Palestine cannot be justified by moral codes. Currently, India has reached a point of comfort with Israel, indicating a significant decline in India's interest in the Palestine issue. Since the end of the Cold War, Indian vocal posturing on the Palestine issue has virtually ceased, with official pronouncements leaning more towards restoring regional peace than an active call for Palestinian rights recognition. With these policy pronouncements, it is unclear whether India retains any leverage in pressing Israel to reach a peaceful solution with Palestine. (Gulrez, 2014, pp. 98–107)

A book chapter titled "*Palestine as a Factor in Indo-Israel Relations*" by Prof. Jawaid Iqbal tries to find out the obstacles posed by Palestine in Indo-Israel relations. India recognized the state of Israel in 1960 but recognition was not followed by the establishment of normal diplomatic relations. During the Cold War years, India's policy towards Israel operated within the framework of the Cold War bi- polar politics. Israel was viewed as an outpost of Western imperialism in the strategic West Asian region. (Iqbal, 2014, pp. 108–127)

As a result, in the conflict between Arab nationalism and Zionism, as exemplified by the Palestinian struggle, India sided with the former. Many top Israeli leaders attempted to persuade Nehru to establish diplomatic relations, but the most he was willing to give was permission for Israel to open an Israeli Consulate in Bombay. The end of the Cold War altered the entire international political landscape. When the Arabs and Israelis started talking, India decided that the time had come to establish diplomatic relations with Israel, which it did in early 1991. Bilateral cooperation between the two countries has grown rapidly since that time.

How the globalization has impacted Indian foreign policy towards Palestine. This issue has been elaborated in a book chapter titled "*Globalization and the shift In India's Palestine Policy*". Author in his

paper notes the negative shift in India's foreign policy towards Palestine. According to him, compulsions of the current phase of globalization played key roles in effecting this shift. Further, the paper demonstrates how both the US and Israel played a crucial role in influencing India's Palestine policy. Thus, in the post- Cold War period, the compulsions of globalization and the predominant role that the US plays in the process have probably forced India to dilute its earlier pro- Palestine policy. (Pradhan, 2008, pp. 286–302)

A Ph. D thesis explores Iran's Palestinian policy after the Islamic Revolution of Iran in 1979. Explaining the Iran's foreign policy during the tenure of Mohammad Reza Shah, the researcher explains the Iranian foreign policy towards Palestine and writes:" Prior to the Islamic revolution, Iran was close with the US and the Israeli government and had an unsupportive policy towards Arabs and Palestinians. The Pahlavi kings both Reza Shah and Mohammad Reza Shah pursued their reluctant policies and conspicuous silence towards Palestine crisis. Pahlavi kings took the full advantage of the Arab and Palestinian troubles and exploited the regional and international environment in their favour. On March 15th, 1950, by granting de-facto recognition to Israel, Mohammed Reza Shah established a regional counter-balance towards the prevention of Arab unity. To achieve a hegemonic position in the Arab region, Shah protracted US and Israeli interests in Iran while supported their unjust policies and occupation of Palestine. He also prevented his people away from making any Islamic solidarity movement with Arab-Palestinian masses". (Khanday, 2020, pp. 172–178)

Researchers have also paid attention towards United States since it plays an important role in the region and always stands firm with Israel on every issue as we have witnessed during the current Hamas-Israel War (October, 2023). A doctoral research tries to examine US role in Israel-Palestine peacemaking during Al-Aqsa Intifada by saying that "since 9/11, the United States' policy towards the Israeli-Palestinian conflict has shifted significantly. The Bush administration directed the State Department to compile a list of Palestinian organizations that have been designated as terrorist organizations. In the meantime, America's campaign against war on terrorism and the subsequent US invasion of Iraq have made an indelible impact on its policy towards the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. Successive US administrations tried to remain an

active partner in the Arab-Israeli peace process to make existence of Israel acceptable to Arab governments. But of late, peace process has been used as a method to deter anti-US terrorism. The significant of the study is that, over the last two decades, no third party has been as involved as the United States in the Palestinian-Israeli peace process".(Imkongmeren, 2008, p. xii)

The role of United Nations becomes very important as far as the Israel-Palestine conflict is concerned. The United Nations was meant as an international instrument to reduce the area of conflict and expand the sphere of peace and stability. The horrors of two world wars had shaken humanity to its core, highlighting the critical need for a shock absorber. The result was the United Nations, which was tasked with saving the world from the third major catastrophe. It was also supposed to be the guardian of international justice and fundamental human rights.

The thesis says "Palestine problem involved not only the question of preventing a local conflict from becoming a major conflagration threatening the peace of the area. It also involved the issue of fundamental human rights of the Palestinians which were being usurped by an alien community. The British Mandatory Government in Palestine was entrusted by the League of Nations to look after the interest of local people and administrative machinery of Palestine".(Sihweil, 1970, p. 9)

PLO, the main political establishment in Palestine has also attracted the Indian research scholars and three doctoral theses have been submitted examining its role in Palestine. A doctoral thesis titled "Israeli Policy towards PLO Since 1974" explores the Israel policy towards Palestinian Liberation Organization. The researcher says that " Israeli policy towards the Palestinian and the PLO has, from the start, been very hostile, aggressive, treating them as refugees and not accepting them. (Ardam, 2003, pp. 85, 276, 280)

A case study has been conducted on the theological debates on Israel-Palestine peace process by a researcher in which the scholar has explained the Islamic Principles of International Conflict Resolution, Religious Aspects of Israel-Palestine Conflict and Peace Process and Islamic Theological Debates on Conflict Resolution and Peace Treaties with Israel.

Islamic scholars and groups within and outside of Palestine possess diverse opinions about the conflict resolution with Israel. Scholars like Jad al-Haq and Ibn-Bazallow reconciliation, scholars like Qardawi oppose peace treaty as long as Israel continues its occupation. While supporters of reconciliation refer to the Hudaibiyya treaty as a model, the critics differentiate between Hudaibiyya and Oslo agreements. Similarly, the supporters point into the Quranic command to "incline towards peace", whereas the critics argue that Israel has not inclined to peace yet. An analysis of the theological debates illustrates that most of the contemporary Islamic scholars permit the coexistence of states with different religious backgrounds. (Shameer, 2020, p. 177)

The creation of Israel in 1948 and the wars related to Arab-Israeli conflict have created a refugee crisis. Palestinian refugees became a big problem for the Arab world. Even today many Palestinians are living in refuge. A doctoral thesis titled "Problem of Palestinian Arab refugees and its impact on politics of West Asia" explains the problems faced by Palestinian refugees and their rights. "The issue of Palestinian refugees is no less serious and significant. Above all, it is a test case for humanity, whether almost the entire population of a country can be deprived of its homeland simply because some people, for whatever reason, have staked a claim on it. Equally significant are the ideological issues at stake in the conflict. On that plane, there is a clash between a group of foreign-born settlers who claim unity based on a specific religion despite vast differences in their ancestry, social and cultural moorings, and competing claims of political allegiance". (Gautam, 1988, pp. 237–252)

Another study on Palestinians in Lebanon titled "*The Changing Socio-Political Status of Palestinians in Lebanon Since 1948*" highlights the status of Palestinians living Lebanon. The partition of Palestine not only led to the Arab-Israeli War in 1948, but it also forced thousands of Palestinians to flee to neighboring Arab countries such as Lebanon, Transjordan, Syria, Egypt, and Kuwait. Marriage and naturalization were also options for obtaining Lebanese citizenship. Since the President of Lebanon has the authority to grant citizenship to some and deny it to others without explanation, as well as to grant citizenship on an individual basis, the President granted 50,000 citizenship to non-camp resident Christian Palestinians, along with a few Muslim elites, in 1973, and 384 elites, both Christian and Muslim Palestinians, in 1994.

The researcher says "according to one researcher who did a study of refugee camps in Lebanon in 1995, two thirds of the Palestinian labour force lived near the agricultural regions in the North and South of Lebanon. The only 10 per cent of registered Palestinians were settled permanently inside Lebanese communities and that most non-camp dwellers (displaced Palestinians) lived near the major UNRWA camps. About 1.5 percent Palestinians held regular jobs in agriculture, animal husbandry and small enterprises in the camps. The remaining Palestinians were Red Crescent and NGO workers. About 95 per cent of Palestinians work forces were largely unemployed".(Ali, 1999, pp. 224–235)

Researchers have also paid attention towards the internal issues of Palestine as a state like politics, education and agriculture. A few doctoral theses discuss these issues to understand the internal dynamics of the state of Palestine for example; a doctoral thesis examines the role of Hamas in Palestinian politics. Hamas has been a major player in Palestinian politics since its inception. The first Palestinian intifada, which began in 1987, triggered the foundation of Hamas. The Intifada could not have lasted as long without Hamas' involvement, and it was Hamas members who helped the Intifada spread throughout the West Bank and Gaza Strip. The continuous military struggle of Hamas has contributed greatly to its growing popularity among Palestinians.

However, its importance in Palestinian politics grew significantly after the Oslo Accords were signed between the PLO and Israel. On political, religious, and economic grounds, Hamas harshly criticized the Accords. Throughout the Oslo period, Hamas pursued a strategy of controlled armed struggle, avoiding direct confrontation with the PNA, which was formed in 1994 as a result of the Oslo Accords.

Hamas' landslide electoral victory in the January 2006 elections surprised the whole world as well as Palestinians. How could it be possible that a "terrorist organization" as it has always been represented in Western media, emerge as a victorious political power? Hamas' chief rival had been the secular Fatah movement, which without interruption for almost a half century dominated the Palestinian political arena. Israel, the United States, European countries, Arab countries and many other regional and international players wanted Fatah to win. Against all expectations, their enemy Hamas triumphed. Hamas' overwhelming victory not only enhanced its role in Palestinian politics, but also provided it with legitimacy for which it was in search of. As a result of

this victory, Hamas formed a National Unity Government and became the leading force in the national liberation struggle. (Ali, 2014, p. 228)

The thesis titled *"Development of a Training Program for the English Teachers of the Secondary Schools in the Context of the New Palestinian Curriculum"* deals with the development of training programmes for English teachers in Palestine. Finally, studying the different factors which help teachers to adopt or reject the new roles and developing suitable pre and in-service training programs which emerge from teachers' needs are of great importance. Hence, looking into these all, it was felt by the researcher that there was a need to conduct a study on developing a training program for teachers of English in the new Palestinian English curriculum. Therefore, he has taken the chance to investigate the same in the West- Bank districts. (Yahya, 2010, p. 220)

Another Ph. D thesis studies the student support system introduced in Al-Quds Open University of Palestine. Al-Quds Open University is an educational institution for Open and Distance Education. Its main job is to transform education to students wherever they may be located and by this way, they can work and learn while at their jobs. Also, it adopts a flexible policy in admission and education of students. (Mousa & Awad, 2011, pp. 16–18)

Another scholar in his doctoral thesis tries to examine the agrarian condition of Palestine focusing on West Bank. The current study is concerned with agricultural development, specifically variations in food grain production and productivity in various regions of Palestine. It is a geographic research conducted in a comparative methodological framework. He says that "Palestine covers an area of 2077000 kms of which about 78 per cent is arable. The remainder consists of bare mountains, deserts and pastures; suitable only for nomads of the total cultivable area 7.8 million hectare about 79 per cent is actually under cultivation". (Ahmad, 1993, pp. 2–3)

The voice of Palestinian resistance literature reaches to very far flung areas in the world. Indian scholars have completed several doctoral theses on different aspects of Palestinian resistance literature and the poetry of Nizar Qabbani and Mahmoud Darwis but most of them are in Arabic language dealing with linguistic aspects. In this regard, a very interesting piece of research is available with us dealing with Palestinian resistance poetry.

Researcher express how the Palestinians utilized literature as an effective tool to express their tragedy and to expose the nature of the colonizer and the real face of the last occupation in the twenty first century which has remained unrevealed due to the cultural siege imposed by the colonizers upon almost every aspect of Palestinian intellectual life. It is written as an expression of pain and hope, believing that the role of literature for any nation during a crisis is beyond question. (Hasanain, 2013, pp. 32–34) Palestinian writers, especially poets, have used popular themes like love, incarceration, and exile to portray their people's suffering.

Analysis

The last quarter of the twelfth century saw a dramatic increase in the numbers of academic writings and researches being carried out in the Indian universities and the research centers as well as in the political science and history department of Indian universities. If one can also add the *madrasah* contributions, the diversity of this literature would be different nature and volume.

Madrasa in Indian context is a place of higher education in Islamic learning where the teaching and research in Quran, Hadith, Fiqh and other branches of Islamic teaching takes place. Madrasas have played a very important role in spearing the Islamic sciences in India. The issue of Palestine remains a very important issue among the Indians and particularly Indians Muslims. There is a huge amount of literature available in Urdu language on different socio-political aspect of Palestine. It is in the form of books, booklets, newspaper articles and research papers. Urdu Newspapers in India is publishing the news about the current Hamas-Israel war on its front pages and editorials often appear in support of the Palestinians and their demand of free Palestine.

While going through the bibliographical literature on Palestine, one can find that the bulk of the writing came primarily in Urdu language that is the most used language by Muslims in India and after the creation of Palestine in 1948. Mutual perceptions and contact between medieval India and the land of Palestine are further needed to be explored by the researchers.

This may provide further scope to understand the general mental images of Palestine among ourselves as we in India have differing opinions on Palestinians and the state of Palestine. We rely on information from

others to inform our impression, images, knowledge, and ultimately, judgment from the Western sources. The issue of Palestine perhaps is one of the most misunderstood, misperceived, and stereotyped issue for common Indian who still think it is place full of militant activities.

Consequently, the general Indians public know about Palestine and the issues related to Israel-Palestine conflict rather negatively, stereotypical, and far from reality. One can also argue that Indian perceptions of Palestinian people, it's nature, religious thoughts very poorly understood, often grossly exaggerated, and frequently attributed to the wrong causes. For, in order to understand the conflict, it is necessary to examine what and how various sections of Indian society, institutions focus on this, especially the reasons behind the creation of Israel.

Conclusion

This paper aims to explore the nature of academic researchers conducted on Palestine in Indian universities. What roles these academic institutions have played in understanding and promoting the India-Palestine relations in contemporary times? This further aims to focus on how the Palestinians and the state of Palestine are being perceived among the Indian academics and researchers, and finally, how the scholarly discourses have been changing with the shift in geo-strategic and economic situations in the Arab world particularly after the warm relation between India and Israel. We also see that the new dimensions and challenges have emerged before the researchers in understanding the issues related to Palestine. The basic questions addressed in this regard are: What are distinct features of the Area Studies Research Centers funded by the government of India? How the Ph. D works have progressed during the last five decades and also, academic discussions on Indo-Palestine relationships have evolved in these research Centers? Moreover, what roles these academic institutions have played in understanding and promoting the India-Palestine relations in contemporary times?

We have also highlighted the major areas of researches in the government funded centre for West Asian Studies functioning at various universities in India. It is worth mentioning that the issue of Palestine is not a very important one among the scholars as compared to other Arab countries. There are a number of reasons behind it. Only those research scholars and academicians took this issue who sympathetically look at

Palestine and Palestinians. We have also discussed the various themes of research works done related to Palestine in India's academic institutions.

As far as the teaching of Palestinian studies in India is concerned, it is worth mentioning that it has not succeeded to acquire importance in academic institutions established for the study of the Arabs. Themes like Israel-Palestine conflict, Refugee crisis, sufferings of Palestinians and other related topics are the part of syllabus but Madrasa in India give a lot of importance to the land of Palestine and particularly Jerusalem simply because of religious reasons. Most of the researches have with bilateral relations between India and Palestine while there are several other themes related to the issue of Palestine that have not been much explored and the topics such as the root causes of Palestine-Israel conflict, sufferings of Palestinians, family structures, social behavior and cultural identity and resolution of the conflict have not been much explored by the scholars.

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